

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF ROAD TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE ON HOUSING PRICES: A CASE STUDY OF IBA LCDA, LAGOS

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Abstract

Effective road infrastructure plays a central role in expanding economic activities, creating options, saving time, and consequently improving the quality of life. Empirical evidence exists to prove that despite its immense benefits, road construction is bound to have both social and economic consequences. In Lagos state, real estate and housing have been the subject of many policies. Despite government efforts, many infrastructural and technological challenges persist that have hampered absolute benefits from being derived. The rising cost of housing in Iba LCDA has become an issue of concern and has created a need to investigate events that could be attributed to this rise. In response, this study examines the relationship between improved road transport infrastructures and housing costs in Iba LCDA. It goes further to highlight the importance of road infrastructure in decision-making regarding housing. The central aim of this study is to determine the extent to which improvements in road transport infrastructure have influenced housing costs in Iba LCDA. To this effect, the study adopts a mixed method approach for data collection and analysis through the combination of questionnaire and key informant interviews. The results revealed that the leading consequence of road development was attributed to high rent as verified by 44.4% of respondents. The interviews corroborated that the relationship between improved road network variables and housing costs in Iba LCDA is a positive one. The key informants also revealed that the extent to which the price of a property would increase depends on certain unique characteristics, such as the distance from the road and accessibility of the property. Another finding is that for some residents, rent has increased as much as four times within the period after road construction. In light of these findings, the study recommends that the government should be involved in the regulation of housing costs to protect the interests of the residents.

Keywords: Effective, Road, Infrastructure, Housing Cost & Transport.

Introduction

Effective road transport networks play a central role in the enhancement of economic activities and the improvement of citizen's quality of life. Improvements in road transport networks have also been attributed as a criterion for sustainable development and form a part of the sustainable development goals (United Nations, 2015). In the same vein, exorbitant prices of land and housing tend to increase social inequality and have the tendency to hamper the process of attaining sustainable development. According to Oni, 2009 both internal and external factors could affect the values of properties and rental costs. Internal factors in this case refer to the physical attributes, such as the size of the room, state of repair, decoration, and facilities which describe the nature of the property. External factors on the other hand, are the characteristics of the city where the property is located such as increase in demand for rental space, location, condition of adjoining properties, nearness to park and leisure, and local and national economic conditions (Olayiwola, Adeleye & Oduwole, 2006; Oni, 2009). For urban residents, their income level is the central feature that determines the cost of housing and their rental outcomes (Pucher & Renne, 2003; Giuliano & Dargay, 2006; Blumenberg & Pierce, 2012). Low-income households have fewer choices in both where they can afford to live and the means of transport available to them given their limited access to personal automobiles (Giuliano, 2005). In Nigeria, the huge demand for affordable housing has constantly been met

with an inadequate supply. In recent times, low-income residents have participated in schemes such as rent-to-own low-cost houses built by the government and the purchase of landed properties by staggered payment plans in developing estates far from the business districts. However, they are faced with the burden of commuting and their accessibility to other parts of the city becomes limited. Nonetheless, intra and inter travel will become a lot easier as the new settlement gradually expands.

Problem Statement

Over time, the relationship between transportation and real estate in urban areas has been the subject of a large body of research (as seen in Dewees, 1976; Chernov & Craig, 2018; Adugbila, 2019). While earlier studies found positive links between transport and property values, other studies maintain that there is a negative relationship. Damm, Lerner-Lam, and Young, 1980, opined that there was a statistically significant relationship between the proximity of land to a train station and land price. Similarly, Chernov & Craig, (2018) suggested that public transit investment increased housing prices in neighbourhoods near where the expansion occurred, but also in neighbourhoods with access to pre-existing segments of the network. However, for Singh, 2005, results revealed that housing property prices decrease immediately around the transport investment or station value uplift through changes in land values. All these conflicting findings create a debate on

whether urban transport plays a critical role in determining housing values (Zhang, Liu, Hang, Yao, & Shi, 2016).

In Iba LCDA, the value of property has tripled over the last decade. This initially was orchestrated by the road construction from Iyana School bus stop through Great Challenge Road, Aratunmi, Last bus stop, Anibaba and down through Iyana Isashi bus stop. While the road construction came with adverse effects such as the loss of some houses and roadside shops owing to the regulatory setback policy, landlords of properties that survived the road construction hiked the rent because the demand for houses and shops increased. Real Estate owners and land grabbers 'Omoniles' became price setters as they began fixing the prices of the limited accommodation and collected rents from two years and above.

Government, as part of her effort to check the activities of greedy landlords, began a property identification process which sought to identify properties and value them correctly for the land use charge. The introduction of the Land Use Charge Law (LUCL) 2001 consolidated the taxes and rates payable under the land rates law, but this caused a hike in rents as property owners transferred the tax cost to the tenants. Furthermore, an adjustment to the Lagos State tenancy agreement was made to protect the rights and interests of both the landlords and tenants. The amendment abolished third-party involvement in land acquisition and required landlords to charge rent for less than a year at once. It also required that tenants use property judiciously and pay up on time and not less than six months' rent at a time (Lagos State Government, 2011). Overall, this agreement reduced the exploitation previously associated with housing and buying land in Lagos.

Despite all these government efforts, many infrastructural and technological challenges persist that have hampered absolute benefits from being derived (Asenime, etal 2012; Durojaiye, 2010; Fagbohun & Oke,

2010). Also, the poor implementation of these policies and the lack of prosecution of erring landowners have left the tenants at the mercy of landlords. This study will therefore examine the effects of road transport infrastructure on housing costs in the Iba Local Council Development Area. Having identified the stated problem, the study shall investigate the relationship between improved road network variables and housing costs and investigate the contributions of other independent variables to housing costs in Iba LCDA.

Significance/ Relevance of this study

In Lagos state and Iba LCDA in particular, transit has entered a phase of rapid expansion over the last decade. The rising cost of real estate in the area has also been an issue of concern. Studies have suggested that property owners and tenants often choose their residences according to neighbourhood characteristics such as price, accessibility to various services, accessibility, pollution, and traffic restrictions (Jordan et al., 2012, Jun et al., 2013, Wang & Li, 2006, Wu et al., 2013, Yang et al., 2013). This study highlights the importance of the transportation system in decisions regarding housing and could affect the accessibility to various services (Babakan & Taleai, 2015).

Study Area

Iba Local Council Development Area is among the thirty-seven Local Council Development Areas (LCDA) established by the Lagos State Government in 2003. It was carved out of Ojo Local Government Area but remains a part of Ojo LGA as an LCDA does not stand alone (Arise News 2024). Its geographical coordinates are 6° 31' 0" North, 3° 12' 0" East.

Iba LCDA has localities spanning the borders of Igbo Elerin, Agboroko, Isashi, and Iba. The area stretches over 15 km and has over 5000 people. (Okwa & Dennis 2015). The area has houses congested together with a well-connected road network. Some parts of the area are swampy and filled with polluted waters.

Figure 1: Map of Iba LCDA

Source: Researcher 2023

Literature Review

Evolution of Road Transportation in Nigeria

In Nigeria, wheel transport was not known until the turn of the last century. Before the arrival of the British administration, the dominant mode of overland transportation was by porters and draught animals over bush paths and neighbouring settlements. The easiest endeavour at transport improvement in the North was directed towards the clearing of paths of about ten to twenty feet wide through the bush, cutting off better drifts at unabridged water and construction of bridges where practicable. Wheeled transport drawn by animals proved a little more costly than porters.

The establishment of the Northern government headquarters at Zungeru necessitated the building of a cart road for mules and oxcarts in 1904 for two major reasons.

- It was hoped that this would reduce the strains thrown on the inland provinces in the provision of porters for the British officials.
- It was believed that the earth-works so created would be suitable for the eventual construction of a light railway.

Lord Lugard originally wanted to build the mule road to Zaria and then on to Sokoto, Katsina and Maiduguri. However, with the authorisation of the Baro-Kano railway line in 1907, the efforts of the Northern government were concentrated on the railway. The cart road was jettisoned at Teginia, 32 km north of Zungeru. With the completion of the Baro-Kano railway in 1909, the government's attention was diverted to Zungeru-Zaria Road, which was eventually completed in 1914.

In the south, where draught animals could not be used because of a tsetse fly invasion, the possibility of motor transport served as an early stimulus to the building of roads. As early as 1903, a superintendent of roads was based in Calabar to begin the survey and construction of roads in the then Eastern provinces (from Calabar-Obubra and Oron-Onitsha). In the West, roads were built to the railway as it was extended north from Lagos. The railway itself extended its service area by constructing roads from its major stations to neighbouring towns.

Nigeria developed her first motorable road in 1906 from Ibadan to Oyo, which thus became linked by a railway-operated road transport service. By the year 1914, there were 3,200km of motorable roads in Nigeria. After the First World War, precisely from 1921, Lagos was linked with Ibadan, Ibadan with Ijebu-Ode. In 1923, Ijebu-Ode was linked with Ilesha, Akure, Ondo, Benin, and joined the Benin-Onitsha- Enugu Road. Although the major towns in the North were linked by roads, the rate of construction was much less than in the South largely because of the availability of donkeys and camels coupled with lower revenue from cash crops. By 1926, there was 4,780 kilometres of roads built and maintained throughout the country. The first bituminous surfacing of road outside the limit of a township took place in the same year and it was a section of the Lagos-Abeokuta road within the Colony province.

Road Transport Infrastructure and Development

Transportation is also very crucial in determining the social and economic activities within and around the settlement. Apart from stimulating the location of settlement, the quantum of economic development in any region is largely determined by the factor of accessibility. The development of transportation is a necessary condition for economic and national development in general. The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) which were in operation from year 2000 to 2015 began as a global effort to tackle poverty, hunger, the spread of disease and to drive expanded levels of education did not give much attention to transport as a major tool for its achievement hence it was replaced with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for years 2016 - 2030 which gave much attention to transport as a major driver for the achievement of its objectives which include eradicating poverty, inequality, preservation of the environment from degradation, improving the justice system as well as the protection of the earth.

Transportation is a major catalyst in the changing process of economic growth and development of any economy. Transport plays a significant role in various aspects of an economy and is thus referred to as the material for developing Africa. Any area requires a certain level of transport infrastructure to maximise its potential. Transportation is an indispensable tool in facilitating economic activities. The development of its infrastructure constitutes an important aspect of life and socio-economic development. Of all the modes of transportation in Nigeria, road transport is dominant, accounting for more than 90 percent of the sub-sector's contribution to the Gross Domestic Product Oyeyemi (2019). The benefits of road transport infrastructure cannot be overemphasised due to its potential to improve infrastructure, employment and affluence, and influence economic and social development (Seo, 2016; World Bank 1994; World Bank 2009). As a result of the contributions of transportation to other sectors of any economy, implementing transport infrastructure into sustainability frameworks has been prescribed as a catalyst for development and poverty reduction globally (Booth, Hanmer, & Lovell, 2000). Thus, road transport infrastructure has become a fundamental driver of economic activities in developing countries.

Consequently, the positive relationship between road transport infrastructure on poverty and development has been the subject of countless research endeavours, especially in sub-Saharan Africa. However, (Gachassin, 2010) had a contrary opinion arguing that investing uniformly in tarred roads in Africa is likely to have a much lower impact on poverty than expected and that isolation from a tarred road is found to have no direct impact on consumption. She concluded that access to roads is only one factor contributing to poverty reduction and not necessarily the most important in many cases. This finding was corroborated by Teravaninthorn & Raballand (2010) who found that in African countries public transport prices are comparatively higher than in other countries in the world, yet most African countries are less developed. Perhaps attributable to the fact that in many African

countries (Nigeria inclusive) road transport infrastructure has severe political underpinnings at the expense of expected developmental agendas. Furthermore, (Seo, 2016) opined that there are downsides to improved road transport infrastructure, making roads able to create nuisance effects and negatively impact housing in the long run. In this study, traffic noise and air pollution through the release of carbon monoxide were cited as some of these negative aspects of road transport infrastructure.

Conceptual Framework

Gentrification has been defined as the restoration of run-down urban areas by the middle class, resulting in displacement of the low-income residents (WordNet, 2006). It refers to the migration of higher income and status groups to lower social status/income neighbourhoods, with the consequent transformation of such areas to higher status neighbourhoods (Atkinson, Wulff, Reynolds, & Spinney, 2011). These descriptions make it apparent that gentrification and challenges with housing, rent and commercial property value are entwined. In many suburbs, developmental endeavours have added aesthetic value while simultaneously hiking housing costs and eliminating affordable rental property. Qualitative reviews by (Atkinson, Wulff, Reynolds, & Spinney, 2011) revealed how gentrification creates social, economic, and emotional problems for those concerned by eliminating their hope of ever owning property. Another effect was pushing renters further into the suburbs, and farther away from amenities and, in extreme cases, leading to internal displacement and homelessness.

Scholars have pointed out that gentrification has less to do with the increase in population and more to do with price (Edlund, Machado, & Sviatschi, 2015; Smith 1979; Xu, 2019), hence affordability of houses in newly developed areas would be an attracting factor and eventually fuel gentrification (Edlund, Machado, & Sviatschi, 2015). This picture was painted clearly by (Xu, 2019) who found that in the period when land prices surged, in Japan, central locations tended to be dominated by commercial development, squeezing out the residential population. After the bursting of the real estate bubble, the shrinking demand for commercial land, in addition to the improving housing affordability, tended to re-adjust the land use trend in central locations, causing the central area residential population to rise again.

Miller and Marshall (1995) as cited in Oyinloye, Olamiju, & Popoola, (2017) in their research on urban renewal strategies in developing nations using Makoko area in Lagos state as their case study, pointed out that “as the years pass, transformations take place, allowing the city to constantly rejuvenate itself in a natural and organic way”. He further stated that the purpose of urban renewal is to change the urban environment deliberately and to inject new vitality through planned adjustment of existing areas to respond to present and future requirements for urban living and working. The study proposed that the situation in Makoko calls for partly rehabilitation and partly total clearance, depending on the level of decadence from street to street as depicted.

Although improved road transport infrastructure leads to an improvement in the quality of life, studies have shown that income level considerably affects the extent to which it does. Poor people tend to be hit hard since they are more likely to be affected by pollution, inaccessibility and the increase in rent (Oppong & Brown, 2012). However, a conflicting twist was introduced by (Oppong & Brown, 2012) and (Xu, 2019). Both papers opined that housing construction and tear-down endeavours in cities are not always influenced by government policies but are financed by individuals engaged in small and medium-scale businesses.

Methodology

This study employed a mixed method for the collection and analysis of data. Questionnaires were used to collect data for quantitative analysis. Secondly, interviews were conducted with respondents who had been serving as real estate agents in Iba LCDA for 10 years and above. This is because their wealth of experience in real estate in general and in Iba, in particular, makes them key informants. This study selected relevant and reliable indicators to measure housing costs about the impact of improved road infrastructure variables. These indicators were selected based on some of the literature reviewed and on the unique characteristics of Iba LCDA.

The questionnaires contained a combination of closed and open-ended questions. The questionnaires covered the property type, services, rent paid, size of land, while the respondents rated the determinant factors in addition to questions on rental values of commercial properties in the past five years. Other questions include an estimate of the percentage increase in rent and factors that influence commercial property values. This study adopted the purposive sampling technique to select the respondents for the key informant interviews while the clustered sampling technique was used for the questionnaire administration with major roads serving as cluster. The clusters include the following roads:

- First gate to Igbo elerin
- Iyana school bus stop to Aratumi
- Iba new site road to Aratumi
- Aratumi to Anibaba
- Anibaba to Iyana Isashi

For each cluster, twenty questionnaires were distributed randomly amongst residents in their homes. A maximum of 3 questionnaires was distributed for every distance of 200 metres (every 5 electric poles – the estimated distance between each pole is 38m). In all, a total of one hundred copies of the questionnaire was administered.

Results

Socio-Economic Profile of Respondents

Culture and poverty still make many Nigerians dependent on their families even as adults. This could be seen in many homes in urban centres in Nigeria. For instance, figures 1 and 2 depict the age distribution, occupation and income of the respondents. The survey shows that the majority (29.3%) of respondents are aged between 40-49 years, which aptly describes the current situation in many households in the study area.

Also, regarding the distribution of respondents by occupation, 39.2% are businessmen, 23.7% are traders, 20.6% are civil servants, 11.3% are artisans, and 5.2%

are students. These 5.2 percent of the population represents a part of the dependent population who are not able to afford their primary needs and as such would need to be dependent on their parents or guardians.

Figure 1: Age and Occupation of the Respondents
Source: Field Survey, 2024

The income bracket that featured the most was N200,001.00 – N300,000.00 with 28%, followed by N100,001.00 to N200,000.00 representing 25% of the population, while only 5% of respondents earned N500,000.00 and above. From the population sample, it can be deduced that the majority of the residents in the study area are poor as they live less than the international poverty line of USD2.15 daily covering food shelter, and clothing. This can be seen using the highest-class limit of the modal income band of N300,000.00 monthly. Thus, it would be impossible for an individual who earns N300,000.00 monthly to plan

for his household (using an average household of 4 in number). Holding other factors constant, the individual would require a minimum of N387,000.00 monthly if he is to live exactly on USD2.15 (rate USD 1 = N1,500.00). This apparently would not be possible as he needs to adjust his spending to give room for education, savings, and other investment purposes. This implies that the level of poverty would be reflected in the housing type of the residents and the accessibility from the major road.

Figure 2: Income of Respondents
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Previous Apartment Versus Current Apartment

The income of the resident and the cost of the apartment are major determinants of the type of residence people live in. The income level determines if the cost of the apartment (whether high or low) can be accommodated by the potential tenant, or if the apartment

type would change. However, as people move to the outskirts of town, farther away from the Central Business District (CBD), the cost of rent would drop significantly when the apartments are compared to like ones around the CBD. This drop in the cost of the apartment would lead to individuals shifting to bigger accommodations when they move farther away from the CBD.

This is evidenced in the comparative bar chart (figure 3) between the respondent’s previous apartment and

their current apartment. Also presented in Figure 4 is the reason for relocation from the previous apartment.

Figure 3: Previous Apartment vs. Current Apartment
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 4: Reason for relocation from previous residence.
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Respondent’s Duration of Stay

As rural settlements begin to experience the basic form of development such as the creation of pathways to serve as roads and electricity, there would be an increasing attraction of the middle class from other locations to such settlements, and as development continues, there will be a total displacement of the initial inhabitants by these middle-income migrants. This description is the case of Iba LCDA showing the gradual displacement of the initial dwellers (see Figure 5).

About 80% of the current residents of the LCDA migrated to the community around 2013 when the road construction commenced or a few years before the road construction when they got information about the proposed road construction. The LCDA only has about 8% of the initial settlers as the majority have been displaced by a new population.

Figure 5: Respondents duration of stay
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Property Distribution by Leasehold

There are different forms of property acquisition. These include outright purchase of the property, inheritance, allotment from the government or by tenancy /lease. The table below shows the distribution.

Table 1

Type of Ownership	Percent
Outright purchase	31.0
Inheritance	10.0
Allotted	5.0
Lease/rent	54.0
Total	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

It is important to state that of the 31% of those who owned properties via outright purchase, 40% of them purchased their properties between 1-5 years, while 26.67% purchased their properties within 6-10 years.

This proves that a greater percentage of landlords migrated to the study area during and after the of the road development as can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6: time of purchase of property
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Cost of owned Properties (before road construction vs. after road construction)

A high influx of migrants into any community forms the basis for the high demand for landed proper-

ties. This would lead to an increase in the price of properties, which further impacts the rents paid for tenanted properties. see Figures 7 and 8.

Figure 7: Cost of properties (land alone)– Before & after road construction
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Rent of Properties (Before road construction Vs. After road construction)

The survey reveals that 54% of the residents of Iba LCDA are in occupation of properties on a rental basis. The rent is paid in advance annually in line with the directive of the Lagos state government. Rents in this community are fixed by the laws of demand and supply for housing. However, the rent of properties could also be influenced by other factors such as the location of the house, quality of finishing of the property, the facilities provided, the condition of the property, the price

for outright purchase of similar properties, the trend of rent increment within the area, the number of bedrooms and bathrooms, etc. Findings also revealed that the rents of properties after the road construction generally increased. Before the road construction, about 51% of the population paid rent between N80,000.00 to N130,000.00 but immediately after the road construction the percentage of residents paying rent in that category dropped by almost 50% and there was an increase in the percentage of residents paying rent between N131,000.00 and above.

Figure 8: Rent of properties – Before & After road construction
Source: Field Survey, 2024

When places begin to experience urbanisation, the cost of accommodation in such places begins to increase due to the competition for land between housing and business units. As a result of this demand for land, property owners are now forced to increase the rent of properties arbitrarily. Our findings revealed that about 50% of tenants have had their rent increase only once

from the inception of their tenancy while 41.9% of those who have experienced multiple rent reviews have had their rent reviewed every year. It was also discovered that over 80% of the population’s rent has been reviewed with a margin of not more than 20% see Figures 9, 10 and 11.

Figure 9: Number of times rent increased
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 10: Interval of rent increase
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 11: Percentage rate of rent increase
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Impact of Road Infrastructure

The major impact of the development of road infrastructure in a rural settlement is gentrification, and this comes with certain negative consequences such as displacement of initial residents, traffic jams and noise pollution from traffic, loss of labour for low-scale jobs, increase in the cost of housing (rent), as well as the emergence of recreation centres. From Figure 12, it can be deduced that the high cost of rent is the predominant consequence of road development. On the other hand,

discussions with residents revealed that crime in gentrified communities was of less impact because of the heightened security that would be available because of the influx of high-income earners into society. Figure 13 further revealed that accessible road is primarily the reason for the emergence of new businesses in gentrified communities and this is closely followed by market population, demand for the output of the business and then the closeness to raw materials.

Figure 12: Consequences of Road development in Iba LCDA
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 13: Reason for business influx
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Results from Qualitative Analysis

The methodology of this study's data collection specifies that both quantitative and qualitative methods were covered. The two methods were used in arriving at the effect that improved road transport infrastructure had on housing costs. In this regard, the qualitative results sought to compensate for the results derived from the questionnaire (quantitative data). As already stated,

the qualitative was conducted using separate key informant interviews to answer the research questions. The verbal responses from some key informants are represented in italics for emphasis.

The results from the key informant interviews reveal that there has been a constant increase in rent and the price of landed property. There is no property in which the rental value has remained the same or decreased in price. Some places have even doubled in

rent. In 2013 it was One Hundred And Twenty Thousand Naira (N120,000.00) for a three-bedroom, but such a flat goes for up to Seven Hundred and Fifty Thousand Naira (N750,000.00) now (Real estate agent practising in Iba LCDA since 2004)

The interviews revealed that the relationship between improved road network variables and housing costs in Iba LCDA is a positive one. Housing costs increased in response to road construction and continued to increase steadily even after. While some respondents in the quantitative survey stated that there was a decrease in prices of property between 8-10million naira after the construction, this finding was debunked by the qualitative review.

“Generally, the prices of property have increased greatly between the time road was constructed and now. The road construction started around 2013, immediately we got the information that the road would be constructed, the prices of property and rent started climbing and has continued to increase after the construction ended”. (School owner, operating in Iba LCDA since 1996)

The key informants also reveal that the extent to which the price of a property would increase depends on certain unique characteristics, such as the state of finishing, and the distance from the road and accessibility of the property. “Prior to the road construction, rents of properties depends on the state of finishing. For example, a two-bedroom flat was between eighty to one hundred thousand (N80000- N100,000) before the road was constructed, but now it could go for up to two hundred and fifty thousand naira (N500,000). The prices of all landed property have increased. Even those in the inner part of town have also increased, due to increased demand for it fuelled by good road. In 2002, one plot of land sold for about two hundred thousand naira (N200,000) as at 2010 it became between two and three million naira. In 2020, it is between nine million and ten million for properties that are not facing the road but at the moment, you can't find bare land. However, you may find someone in distress that is willing to sell a built-up property for no less than N35m depending on its proximity to the road.” (Real estate agent practising in Iba LCDA since 1999).

Findings

The central aim of this study was to determine whether the road construction in the Iba LCDA area of Lagos State had any effect on housing costs within the area. Findings from the study revealed that there is a positive relationship between road improvements and housing costs as there has been an increase in housing costs due to the road improvement. The study compared the housing cost in terms of rents paid before the road construction and the rents paid after the road construction in year 2013. The results from both the respondents and facts gathered from personal interviews revealed that within each category of accommodation, a greater percentage of respondents claimed that they have paid higher rents after the road construction than what they paid before the road construction. The key informants also stated emphatically that no property has maintained the same value both for rent and sale.

The benefits of the mixed method employed by this study are validated in the way the qualitative review filled the gap created by the quantitative review. As shown in the analysis, other consequences of the road improvement aside from the hike in rents were traffic jams, noise pollution and increased crime rate. However, holding road improvement constant, explanatory variables such as improved housing facilities, search for cheaper accommodation, population explosion, and increased business opportunities have also led to the high demand for housing units within the study area and the resultant effect of these is also seen in high rent.

Conclusion

Given the findings, it can be concluded that improvement in road infrastructure has a positive effect on housing costs. This confirms the position of Awaworyi Churchill (2021) that transport infrastructure investments will accompany house price growth, deepening income inequality associated with it as well as guide policy decisions at the micro-level. The study aligns with the position of Adugbila (2019) that road expansion influenced and shaped residential development by opening and linking them to other parts of the city. The study also reveals the absolute concept of gentrification as the LCDA is fast becoming urbanised due to the influx of individuals, businesses and other social services that would support a sustainable settlement and these stem from the improvement in the road infrastructure. Contrary to the opinion of Brinkman and Lin, (2019), that transport infrastructure could cause slower growth in some areas, decreasing land values and house prices the study proved otherwise as a major consideration for the selection of housing accommodation by residents of Lagos is the proximity to transport infrastructure, especially road transport mode.

Recommendations

The study recommends sensitisation of residents about the provisions of the Land Use Charge Law (LUCL) 2001 and the Lagos State Tenancy Agreement of 2011 to guard against the continuous upward review of rents and other forms of exploitation by greedy landlords as a result of road infrastructure improvement. The study recommends that the government should be involved in regulating rent in Iba LCDA and also make adequate provision for the maintenance of the road infrastructure and other amenities to prevent eroding the value of the amenities by the teeming migrants. Regulated low-cost housing schemes for the middle class with the option of a mortgage should be explored. This will guard against population explosion and overuse of infrastructures in communities that have been gentrified. Further studies are also recommended to determine how the road infrastructure has imparted transportation within the area, and how traffic can be managed well. The study can also be duplicated in other LCDAs in Lagos state, to inform transport and housing policies that are tailored to suit the needs of LCDA'S.

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